

TABLE 2

Compound	N-H frequencies (cm^{-1})		O-H frequencies (cm^{-1})		-N=N- frequencies (cm^{-1})
OHBANM=L	3325	3260			1585
NaIN ₂ N.L	3325	3125	2450	1960	1525
KIN ₂ N.L	3325	3150-25	2450	1920	1505
NaONP.L	3325	3125	2400	1940	1510
KONP.L	3325	3115	2400	1860	1507
Na ₂ H ₃ N ₄ .L	3300	3225	2400	1880	1530
K ₂ H ₃ N ₄ .L	3325	3125	2400	1880	1530
Na ₈ HQ.L	3350(br)				1505
Na ₈ AlH.L			2380	1860	1500
K ₈ Al ₄ .L			2380	1860	1505

br = broad.

frequencies show up as one or two broad humps, one at $\sim 2500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the other at $1800-1960 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. It suggests strong association of the OH group.

The -N=N- stretching frequency at 1535 cm^{-1} in the ligand has been spotted between 1525 cm^{-1} to 1500 cm^{-1} in the adducts, suggesting again the association of -N=N- group in the alkali metal adducts.

Our present work also shows that strong intra-molecular hydrogen bonding existing in the ligand breaks on complexation. It has been further observed that ligands, which have stronger intra-hydrogen bonding, form stable alkali metal adducts.

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Interaction Products of Triphenylphosphine Oxide with Some Organotin Halides

K. K. BAJPAI*

Indian Institute of Sugarcane Research, Lucknow-226 002
and

BEENA BAJPAI

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow,
Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 17 December 1980, revised 31 December 1981, accepted 8 July 1982

COMPLEXES of triorganophosphine oxide with a variety of metal salts have been extensively studied¹⁻⁸. Syntheses and characterisation of adducts of the Lewis base with organometallic moieties have also been reported⁹⁻¹⁶. Molecular

addition compounds of triphenylphosphine oxide (TPPO) with organotin moieties appear not to have received adequate attention. In continuation of our studies on organotins¹⁷⁻²¹, we report here the interaction of TPPO with some organotins which yielded molecular addition compounds of the type $R_n\text{SnX}_{4-n}\cdot\text{L}$ (R=phenyl or butyl; X=Cl or Br, n=1,2 or 3 and L=TPPO). The compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis, melting point and their data on conductance, molecular weight, ir and mass spectrometry have been discussed.

Experimental

Di or triorganotin halides were prepared according to literature methods²². TPPO (Carlsile) and other reagents of analytical grade (B.D.H./S. Merck) were used without further purification.

In a typical reaction, 2 m mole of an organotin derivative and equimolar amount of TPPO were refluxed in 40 ml of benzene/chloroform for about 1 hr. A suitable volume of pet. ether (60-80)/ether was added to this (in some cases reaction mixture was kept in a fridge) and the solid so obtained was separated, washed with pet. ether, recrystallised from benzene-pet. ether solvent pair and dried under vacuum. The yield was about 66%.

The m. ps. of the adducts were determined on electrically operated apparatus (M/s. Toshniwal Bros., Bombay). Elemental analyses were done by micro analytical method but tin was estimated as stannic acid. The metal was weighed as oxide after ignition.

The infrared spectra of TPPO and their adducts with organotins were recorded in the region 4000-200 using Perkin Elmer IR spectrophotometer, model 521. Calibration was performed with a polystyrene film.

Conductance was measured in benzene by Phillips, type PR 9500, conductivity bridge using dip type conductivity cell having a cell constant 0.7584. The molecular weights of the adducts were determined cryoscopically in benzene. Mass spectrometer, Hitachi model No. RMU-6E, was used for obtaining mass spectra.

Results and Discussion

Experimental data of the adducts are given in Table 1. The adducts melt in the range of $62-175^\circ$ while $\text{Ph-SnCl}_3\cdot\text{TPPO}$ do not melt up to 250° . They are soluble in common organic solvents, are thermally stable and do not decompose when heated to their m. ps. for several hr. They are insensitive to atmospheric moisture but easily hydrolyse when refluxed with water or aqueous ammonia yielding polymeric organotin oxide as the final product. The conductance values in $10^{-3}M$ solutions indicate

* Author for correspondence.

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR TRIPHENYLPHOSPHINE OXIDE (L) OF ORGANOTIN HALIDES

Adducts	m.p. (°C)	Sn	C	N	Mol. wt.	IR absorption (cm ⁻¹)	
						νP=O	νSn-O
Ph ₃ SnCl ₂ .L	>250	20.2 (20.4)	50.0 (49.6)	3.2 (3.4)	450 (581)	1145 m	320 s
Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .L	175	19.4 (19.1)	57.6 (57.8)	4.2 (4.0)	422 (622)	1140 s	318 s
Ph ₂ SnBr ₂ .L	158	15.4 (16.7)	50.6 (50.6)	3.1 (3.5)	602 (711)	1135 s	315 s
Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .L	170	17.1 (17.9)	66.8 (66.5)	4.7 (4.5)	510 (664)	1155 s	320 s
BuSnCl ₂ .L	88	20.9 (21.2)	47.3 (47.1)	4.2 (4.3)	400 (560)	1150 s	325 s
Bu ₂ SnCl ₂ .L	62	20.3 (20.4)	53.5 (53.6)	5.6 (5.7)	487 (582)	1153 s	335 s
Bu ₂ SnBr ₂ .L	78	18.4 (17.7)	46.3 (46.5)	5.1 (4.9)	498 (671)	1148 m	322 m

Figures in parenthesis are the calculated values ; m=medium, s=strong.

the absence of ionic species and their observed low molecular weight, compared to formulae weight, suggest significant dissociation in solution.

As per equation below, the interaction of the adducts with some Lewis bases such as 1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridine, dimethylsulfoxide, pyridine-N-oxide was investigated in chloroform pet. ether. The complete substitution of TPPO molecule by the above bases indicates its comparatively poor donor ability towards the investigated Lewis acids. These replacements were confirmed by elemental analyses, m. ps. and infrared data of the adducts.

(L=1,10-phen, 2,2'-bipy, py-N-oxide or DMSO)

Mass spectra* of three adducts having different Lewis acid species (C₆H₅)₂SnCl, (C₆H₅)₂SnCl₂ and (C₄H₉)₂SnCl₂ were recorded as an aid to their characterisation and to study their fragmentation pattern. On electron impact, the adducts readily break up into their Lewis acid and Lewis base fragments viz. [(C₆H₅)₂SnCl]⁺ (m/e 386) or [(C₆H₅)₂SnCl₂]⁺ (m/e 344) or [(C₄H₉)₂SnCl₂]⁺ (m/e 304) and [(C₆H₅)₂PO]⁺ (m/e 278) while the molecular ions were not observed. This indicated a weak linkage between the acids and the base forming the adducts. The fragment [(C₆H₅)₂PO]⁺ gave rise to smaller fragments m/e 201 [(C₆H₅)₂PO]⁺, 108 [C₆H₅P]⁺, 47[PO]⁺, 31[P]⁺ on further cleavage. The fragmentation pattern of [(C₆H₅)₂SnCl]⁺, [(C₆H₅)₂SnCl₂]⁺ and [(C₄H₉)₂SnCl₂]⁺ was dissimilar and gave mass spectral peaks (m/e) as per schemes given below :

* The mass spectral fragments under consideration refer to appropriate combination of abundant isotopes for Sn and Cl.

The most significant absorption in the infrared spectra of TPPO and its adducts, the P=O stretching frequency appearing as a strong band at 1190 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the Lewis base, undergoes a negative shift of 37 cm⁻¹ to 55 cm⁻¹ on adduct formation. This lowering of P=O is indicative of coordination^{7-9,13,14}.

A new spectral band of strong intensity has been observed in a close range of 315-335 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of adducts which was not present either in the spectra of TPPO or the Lewis acids. This band may possibly be associated with vibration of O→Sn. Sn-Cl and Sn-aryl stretches have been found at the known positions in the spectra of the Lewis acids^{17,18}. A significant lowering of Sn-Cl stretching in the adducts characteristically depicts increase in the coordination number of the metal atom.

Investigations revealed some important biological properties of the adducts and the findings will be reported elsewhere.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for financial support to one of them (B.B.) and the Head, Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow for the facilities. They are also thankful to Shri R. K. Singh, Medicinal Chemistry Division, C. D. R. I., Lucknow for a discussion on mass spectrometry.

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Mixed Ligand Cobalt(III) Complexes Containing Benzotriazole or 5-Nitrobenzotriazole

L. K. MISHRA and HIMANSHU BHUSHAN

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005
and

N. K. JHA†

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology,
New Delhi-110 016

Manuscript received 3 August 1981, revised 6 February 1982,
accepted 27 May 1982

COMPLEXING behaviour of benzotriazole¹⁻⁴ and its use in estimation of some transition metal ions⁵⁻⁷ are well known. Preparation of mixed ligand Co(III) complexes of benzotriazole and of 5-nitrobenzotriazole from *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl₂]Cl and [Co(NH₂)₂(NO₂)₂Cl] and their characterization by electronic and ir spectral study and magnetic measurements are reported in this paper.

Experimental

Trans-[Co(en)₂Cl₂]Cl⁸, [Co(NH₂)₂(NO₂)Cl]⁹ and benzotriazole⁸ were prepared by reported methods and 5-nitrobenzotriazole was prepared by a modification of the method for benzotriazole.

[Co(en)₂(Bt)*Cl]Cl (rose red) and [Co(en)₂(NO₂-Bt)Cl]Cl (orange red) were obtained by treating an

aqueous solution of [Co(en)₂Cl₂]Cl with an aqueous ethanolic solution of benzotriazole and 5-nitrobenzotriazole respectively in 1 : 1 molar ratio and adjusting the pH to 7 with dil. NaOH. [Co(NH₂)₂(NO₂)₂(Bt).H₂O (orange yellow) and [Co(NH₂)₂(NO₂)₂(NO₂-Bt)].1.5H₂O (dull orange yellow) were prepared in a similar way from [Co(NH₂)₂(NO₂)₂Cl]. [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl] 1.2H₂O (orange red) was precipitated by adding a saturated aqueous solution of KI to an aqueous solution of [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl]Cl.

Cobalt in the complexes was estimated as cobalt sulphate after igniting the complex and treating the residue with conc. HNO₃ and conc. H₂SO₄. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's semi-micro method. Water of crystallization was determined by heating the complex below 120° and chlorine was estimated as AgCl by decomposing the complex in presence of AgNO₃. C and H analyses were obtained from microanalytical laboratory.

Magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Guoy method using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as standard. Effective magnetic moments were calculated after making diamagnetic correction using Pascal's constants¹¹. Conductivity measurements of aqueous solutions were done on a conductivity bridge (Toshniwal, India). Electronic spectra were recorded on a Hilger Watts Uvispek spectrophotometer H700. Infrared spectra (4000-650 cm⁻¹) were recorded in KBr discs on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Substitution products from trans-[Co(en)₂Cl₂]Cl: The analytical data of the complexes are reported in Table 1. The complexes are slightly soluble in water but almost insoluble in methanol or ethanol. They are diamagnetic suggesting the presence of octahedral low spin Co(III)¹². Δ_M values of freshly prepared 10⁻³ M aqueous solutions of [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl]Cl and [Co(en)₂(NO₂-Bt)Cl]Cl were 125 and 130 ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, respectively which are in the range of 1 : 1 electrolytes¹³. The conductance gradually increased on standing which may be due to aquation e.g. [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl]²⁺ + H₂O = [Co(en)₂(Bt)(H₂O)]²⁺ + Cl⁻.

These complexes show only one weak band around 500 nm (Table 1) except [Co(en)₂(Bt)Cl]Cl which displays an additional shoulder at 370 nm. The weak band corresponds to ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and the shoulder to ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} transition of low spin octahedral Co(III) complexes¹⁴. Higher λ_{max} values for the solid state than for the solution (Table 1) indicate lower symmetry in solid than in solution. *Cis*- and *trans*-isomers of the complexes of the type [CoA₄BC]²⁺ can be differentiated by ε_{max} values of these bands¹⁵, e.g. ε_{max} values of ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} bands of *cis*-[Co(en)₂Cl₂]²⁺ and *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)(Cl)]²⁺ are 89 and 90 compared to 41 and 40 for the corresponding *trans*-complex^{15,16}.

† Author for correspondence. * BtH = benzotriazole.